

Exploring the barriers and facilitators to the success of MSCA projects: a focus group-based study

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Context of the survey

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) constitute one of the European Union's most distinguished frameworks for advancing research excellence, researcher mobility, and high-quality skills development across all scientific disciplines. Positioned as a central instrument of the European Research Area, the MSCA supports the creation of a highly skilled, adaptable, and internationally competitive research workforce. The program is founded on the principle that international, interdisciplinary, and intersectoral mobility is essential for developing researchers capable of addressing societal, scientific, and technological challenges. MSCA funding schemes promote structured, researcher-centered training environments that combine scientific excellence with in-depth professional development. All MSCA actions place strong emphasis on open science practices, responsible research and innovation, equality and inclusion, and engagement with non-academic stakeholders.

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Networks, previously known as the Innovative Training Networks, bring together consortia of at least three organizations from different countries and sectors to deliver joint PhD training programs (European Commission, 2025). These networks aim to cultivate researchers with strong interdisciplinary skills, an entrepreneurial mindset, and practical experience across both academic and non-academic settings, including industrial doctorates and joint degree opportunities (European Commission, 2025). Postdoctoral Fellowships, formerly Individual Fellowships, provide funding for research projects lasting 12–24 months, either in Europe or globally, with a compulsory return phase for international placements. They support professional growth by offering cross-border, intersectoral, and interdisciplinary training, as well as optional involvement in non-academic environments

(European Commission, 2025). Staff Exchanges, previously known as the Research and Innovation Staff Exchange, promote short-term mobility, ranging from one to twelve months, for researchers, technical staff, and administrative personnel. They strengthen collaboration and facilitate the transfer of knowledge between academic institutions, industry, and other sectors (European Commission, 2025). The COFUND scheme co-finances regional, national, or international doctoral and postdoctoral programs that adhere to MSCA principles, such as open recruitment, structured training, and international mobility. Typically, these programs operate with budgets of around EUR 10 million (European Commission, 2025). Lastly, the MSCA and Citizens program encourages public engagement with research through activities such as the European Researchers' Night and Researchers at Schools, aiming to foster curiosity and interest in science, especially among young audiences (European Commission, 2025).

IANUS project

The Integrative MSCA Achievements and Networks for Unified Strategies (IANUS) project seeks to maximize the strategic contribution of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) to the European Union's Missions and the European Research Area (ERA) by:

- monitoring and evaluating the extent to which MSCA projects support the EU Missions and ERA policy Action 4 (promoting attractive research careers and mobility), Action 7 (enhancing knowledge transfer and valorisation), and Action 9 (fostering international cooperation), while fostering synergies with other relevant EU initiatives;
- promoting interaction and collaboration among MSCA beneficiaries, researchers, and policymakers;
- identifying researchers' training and skills requirements, highlighting best practices and success stories, and providing practical and policy recommendations to enhance MSCA's impact and intersectoral cooperation.

Study aim

MSCA fellows face a range of challenges that can significantly influence their career development and mobility. Among the most frequently reported are financial constraints, as fellowship stipends may not fully cover living costs, housing, and family-related obligations, including childcare (European Commission, 2017). Their experiences are further influenced by the considerable variability in institutional support across host organizations, including access to housing assistance or other forms of local financial and logistical support, which can help

alleviate some pressures associated with relocation, cost of living, and family obligations, but do not always fully resolve these challenges (European Commission, 2021). While most fellows consider MSCA funding adequate, a notable minority reports that allowances fall short of essential expenses, particularly in high-cost countries or for those with dependents (European Commission, 2017). These findings underscore the need for holistic support mechanisms that extend beyond mentorship and training, encompassing financial, accommodation, and family-related assistance to ensure equitable participation and sustainable career development.

This focus group study, conducted within the IANUS project, aims to better understand the real-world experiences and needs of MSCA beneficiaries and stakeholders. By examining intersectoral collaboration and training gaps, the study aims to uncover barriers and facilitators that affect research quality and career development. This evidence is crucial for designing practical, project-specific interventions that strengthen cooperation between academia and the business sector and enhance the overall impact of MSCA projects within the IANUS framework.

Review of the literature

Quality and relevance of MSCA training

MSCA mobility programs aim not only to enhance research output but also to support researchers' broader professional development. Training in research mobility programs typically includes technical, soft, and interdisciplinary or cross-sectoral skills (Andreoli *et al.*, 2024). Technical training may cover laboratory techniques, programming, or advanced data analysis, while soft skills encompass scientific writing, public speaking, grant writing, and team leadership. Interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral experiences foster collaboration across fields and encourage innovation. Each type of training brings distinct benefits: technical skills strengthen core expertise, soft skills improve adaptability, and interdisciplinary exposure broadens researchers' perspectives. Nonetheless, challenges remain, such as the narrow focus of technical training, the undervaluation of soft skills, and communication barriers in interdisciplinary work. A recent survey (European Commission, 2025) also indicated growing attention to transferable skills such as communication, leadership, and administrative competence. At the same time, researchers themselves highlighted additional skills crucial for their career development, including advanced project management, strategic career planning, enhanced intersectoral collaboration, and entrepreneurial abilities.

End-of-fellowship surveys consistently show high satisfaction with the quality and relevance of MSCA training: around 98% of fellows report using the skills acquired, and 86% rate the training as good or very good (European Commission, 2025). Approximately one-third gain experience outside academia, and two years later, 95% indicate that this experience positively contributed to their careers, with 54% reporting a significant benefit. Despite these overwhelmingly positive outcomes, survey data alone cannot explain why a small proportion of fellows (14%) do not consider the training useful, highlighting the need for a deeper investigation into unmet needs and structural barriers. Numbers can show the extent of satisfaction, but cannot uncover the underlying reasons for dissatisfaction, specific gaps in skills, or systemic obstacles.

Mentorship remains a critical component of career support. Lambert *et al.* (2023) identified structural mentoring barriers at institutional, interpersonal, and individual levels in postdoctoral training, highlighting how structured mentorship networks and professional development programs enhance research success. Similarly, Thakar *et al.* (2024) demonstrated that targeted mentorship significantly improves career self-efficacy and commitment, even in quantitative survey-based research. Although these studies were not conducted within MSCA programs, their findings are highly relevant for designing mentorship strategies that complement existing training and strengthen researchers' confidence, professional skills, and long-term engagement in research. While MSCA programs provide a strong foundation, aligning training more closely with the skills researchers themselves identify as essential could further enhance career outcomes and long-term employability. Here, we sought to explore which skills beneficiaries find most useful and which they perceive as less relevant.

Career development and employment

MSCA programs play a central role in supporting researchers' mobility, which is widely recognized as a cornerstone of career development within the European Research Area. Existing evidence consistently shows that mobility enhances research productivity, fosters international collaboration, and broadens researchers' skill sets (European Commission, 2022). At the same time, mobility is associated with structural challenges, including job insecurity, limited reintegration opportunities, and unequal access across disciplines and regions.

According to a recent survey of MSCA beneficiaries (European Commission, 2025), 91% of participants reported a positive impact of the program on their career development, and the vast majority indicated that the skills acquired during the mobility period were applicable in subsequent positions. Employment outcomes are also strong: 57% of fellows are employed at

the end of their fellowship, increasing to 87% two years later. Most are engaged in research-related roles, with 44% holding permanent or open-ended contracts. Unemployment rates are lower among experienced researchers than among doctoral candidates (2% compared to 9%). Despite these generally positive outcomes, qualitative studies point to persistent concerns regarding long-term career security and institutional belonging (Czeranowska *et al.*, 2023). These concerns are often linked to fixed-term contracts, demanding promotion criteria, and the highly competitive nature of academic environments, which can undermine researchers' sense of stability and inclusion.

Broader research trends further emphasise the challenges faced by early-career researchers. A persistent mismatch between the number of doctoral graduates and the availability of academic positions (Hnatkova *et al.* 2022) highlights the growing necessity of preparing researchers for diverse career paths beyond academia. In this context, encouraging transitions to the private and public sectors is increasingly important, as holding a PhD no longer guarantees access to academic positions. MSCA programs can play a key role in this regard by fostering transferable skills and promoting intersectoral collaboration.

Examining career development and employment outcomes within MSCA programs is particularly timely in light of ongoing transformations in academic labour markets and EU research and innovation policy. As research careers become increasingly international, project-based, and competitive, understanding how mobility programs influence long-term employment trajectories is essential for ensuring that such initiatives contribute to sustainable and inclusive research careers. In this context, our research could help inform evidence-based policy decisions aimed at strengthening career prospects for early-career researchers, improving the alignment between doctoral training and labour market needs, and maximising the societal and economic returns of public investment in researcher mobility.

Intersectoral collaboration

Intersectoral collaboration within the MSCA framework brings together the academic and non-academic sectors, such as industry or small- and medium-sized enterprises, to strengthen researcher training, knowledge transfer, and innovation through mobility and joint projects. Collaboration between academia and industry is widely recognized as a key mechanism for transforming research outcomes into practical innovation (European Commission, 2017).

As the number of academic positions remains limited, many PhD graduates increasingly need to explore career paths beyond academia (Hnatkova *et al.*, 2022). This trend highlights the

growing importance of intersectoral collaboration in doctoral training. By fostering partnerships between universities and industry, such programs expose researchers to real-world challenges, provide practical experience, and build networks that extend beyond the academic environment. This approach enhances the relevance of the training, broadens researchers' career opportunities, and equips them with transferable skills that are highly valued across sectors. Ultimately, intersectoral collaboration helps prepare versatile researchers capable of driving innovation both within and outside academia, with about one-third of fellows gaining non-academic experience *via* secondments (European Commission, 2024). Researchers gain essential transferable skills, such as project management and interdisciplinary competencies, improving their employability and long-term career prospects. At the same time, host organizations benefit by attracting talented researchers and establishing lasting international partnerships, as seen in Staff Exchanges involving 300 non-academic entities across 111 countries (European Commission, 2024).

According to the European Commission's 2017 report, the number of businesses interested in participating in the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) has been steadily increasing over time (European Commission, 2017). To date, more businesses have applied to participate in MSCA under Horizon 2020 than during the entire FP7 programming period. Notably, around 47% of H2020 MSCA business participants had not previously been involved in MSCA during FP7, highlighting the program's success in attracting new business participants and expanding its reach. However, results from the European Commission indicate that the share of fellows gaining experience in the non-academic sector in 2024 has not increased compared to 2023, remaining at approximately one-third of all participants, most commonly through short-term secondments. Also, the level of participation still varies according to scientific fields and sectors.

Given this stagnation, our project will investigate the underlying factors that hinder deeper and more sustained intersectoral collaboration. Through these focus groups, we aim to identify the barriers that researchers and host organisations face, understand why engagement with the non-academic sector remains limited, and explore what conditions are necessary to strengthen long-term cooperation.

Research reproducibility

Finally, research reproducibility, referring to obtaining consistent results using the same data and methods (National Academies of Sciences, 2019), has become a central concern across scientific disciplines. Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) supports research excellence

through principles like open science and responsible research practices, which indirectly promote reproducibility *via* transparent methodologies and data sharing (European Commission, 2025). While no direct MSCA policy mandates reproducibility checks, evaluations emphasize standardized proposal reviews to reduce evaluator disagreement, enhancing funding decision reliability akin to reproducible outcomes. Despite increasing policy support for open science and the adoption of FAIR data principles, practices that promote reproducibility, such as preregistration, transparent reporting, and open sharing of data and code, remain unevenly implemented (National Academies of Sciences, 2019).

In light of these challenges, our study focuses on understanding how researchers perceive the importance of reproducibility and what concrete steps they have taken to ensure it in their own work. By investigating these perceptions and behaviors, we aim to identify current gaps between recommended practices and actual implementation, providing insight into how reproducibility can be better supported across scientific communities.

While quantitative evaluations of MSCA programs provide valuable insights into outcomes such as employment, training satisfaction, and mobility, they do not fully explain why some fellows report dissatisfaction or unmet needs, nor do they capture the complex contextual factors that shape career development and research experiences. Understanding these experiences is essential for identifying the challenges fellows face, the support mechanisms that are effective, and the areas where program design could be improved. This study aims to fill this gap by generating rich, contextualized insights into the perspectives, challenges, and needs of MSCA beneficiaries and stakeholders. By using focus groups, participants can articulate their experiences in their own words, reflect on the aspects of their training and mobility that were most impactful, and point out specific shortcomings in program implementation. Previous studies employing thematic analysis in the context of researcher mobility have highlighted recurring themes such as skill acquisition, career visibility, and professional development, which closely align with the overarching goals of MSCA (Ploszaj, 2025). By integrating these qualitative insights with existing quantitative evidence, the study can inform targeted, project-specific interventions. Such interventions have the potential to enhance training quality, strengthen mentorship practices, foster intersectoral collaboration, and equip fellows with the knowledge, skills, and networks required to transition successfully into a range of research and innovation roles. In doing so, the research contributes not only to improving individual career trajectories but also to advancing the broader objectives of European research and innovation policy.

Methods

Through a minimum of 10 focus group consisting of 6 participants, we will explore the barriers and facilitators to the success of MSCA projects among MSCA beneficiaries.

Research questions/topics:

These focus groups will explore the perceived barriers and facilitators to the following domains: professional development/career advancement/visibility; training quality; leadership and working conditions; intersectoral collaboration; research reproducibility; skills for societal change. They will follow a preliminary topic guide that is submitted alongside this preregistration, which is subject to change following its piloting in the first focus group.

Anticipated duration

March to July 2026.

Design plan

Study design

Qualitative, focus group-based study.

Sampling and case selection strategy

Participants for the focus groups will be identified and recruited through a purposive sampling strategy to ensure representation of key stakeholder groups involved in the MSCA community. The target participants will include MSCA fellows, supervisors, representatives from the REA and national contact points, as well as stakeholders from the business and non-academic sectors who have experience in intersectoral collaboration and research implementation. To capture a broad range of perspectives, we will recruit participants across disciplinary backgrounds, from different regions/countries, and from different types of organizations (academic, private, public, or non-profit).

Potential participants will be identified from the survey analysis, portfolio analysis, existing project databases, institutional networks, personal contacts, and publicly available information from MSCA-funded projects. Supervisors and fellows will be contacted directly through institutional email invitations distributed by project coordinators or consortium leads, or collected in the survey. Representatives from REA and the business sector will be approached through professional contacts and collaboration networks established within the IANUS project.

As we will not be able to connect the participants to their survey responses due to reasons of anonymity, they will be asked to fill out a short questionnaire prior to each focus group. Aside from their basic demographic data (age, sex, country, level of education, employment status/current work position, role in the MSCA), this questionnaire will require them to rank, by priority for their project, the domains of success investigated in the survey. We will then explore the two highest-ranked domains in their focus groups, which will keep the discussions focused on what the participants believe to be relevant for them, rather than what we assume might be so. To ensure that all domains are covered appropriately, we will perform interim analyses after each focus group. When we observe data saturation in a specific domain, we will exclude it from the subsequent pre-focus group questionnaire, limiting participants' number of choices and ensuring that "unprioritized" topics are also covered in the discussions.

Data collection

Data source(s) and data type(s)

Data type: original data

Data source: MS Teams recordings and transcripts of the focus groups

Data collection methods

Each potential participant will receive an invitation letter *via* email outlining the purpose of the study, the expected time commitment, confidentiality assurances, ethical considerations, as well as a questionnaire containing the study questions. Participation will be entirely voluntary, and informed consent will be obtained from all participants before data collection.

The subsequent focus groups will be conducted online (*via* Microsoft Teams) in English among fellows, supervisors, MSCA REA, and DG EAC representatives, and stakeholders from the business sector, and will last up to 90 minutes. One researcher will lead the focus group sessions, guiding the discussion and ensuring that all topics in the interview guide are covered. A second researcher will act as an observer, taking notes on group dynamics and interactions. The focus groups will be recorded and transcribed using Teams' internal tools for the data analysis.

Stopping criteria

We will cease collecting data when we achieve data saturation, *i.e.*, when we observe that no new units/codes/themes are appearing from the data during the collection phase, based on interim surface-level analyses of the transcripts.

Analysis plan

Data analysis approach

Two researchers (one from the FFST and one from the MEFST team) will independently analyze the transcripts of the focus group sessions through Graneheim and Lundman's content analysis methodology (Graneheim & Lundman, 2004). In detail, they will read the transcripts several times and take notes in the process. They will then code "meaning units", assigning implicit or explicit meaning to words, phrases, and sentences in the transcripts. Afterwards, they will revise these units, condensing them and coding them, and will eventually place them in larger (sub)categories. This process will be repeated and discussed several times by the two researchers, after which concrete subthemes and themes will be formed. Data collection will continue until successive transcripts no longer yield new or substantively different insights, indicating that data saturation has been reached. At this point, further data collection will be discontinued, as additional data would be unlikely to enhance the analytical framework. Lastly, these themes and subthemes will be discussed within the whole team. The final findings will be presented descriptively based on the themes/subthemes and will be accompanied by the participants' anonymized quotations. The analysis itself will be performed in Taguette software (Rampin & Rampin, 2021), as well as a questionnaire containing the study questions.

Ethics

All focus group recordings and transcripts will be securely stored on password-protected servers managed by the partner institution. Access to the data will be restricted to members of the research team directly involved in the study. Participant identities will be pseudonymized to enable analysis, while confidentiality will be maintained externally. Any identifying information within the focus group transcripts will likewise be anonymized and deidentified.

Data management will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation and institutional data protection policies. Original recordings will be retained for a maximum of five years after project completion and then permanently deleted.

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